

PERIDYNAMICS FOR HOMOGENIZATION AND DAMAGE TENSOR IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a peridynamic unit cell approach to predict the effective properties of micro-structures in the presence of many defects and voids, and complex heterogeneity. It permits arbitrary number of constituent materials, voids and cracks. The constituent materials can have orthotropic response to account for deformation coupling. Voids and cracks can be modeled by simply breaking the peridynamic bonds between the material points. Also, the periodic boundary conditions are applied in a natural way without any constraint conditions. Furthermore, it leads to the determination of a damage matrix necessary for progressive failure analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are intrinsically heterogeneous at the microscopic length scale. However, they appear to be homogeneous at the macroscopic length scale, and require an efficient way to perform structural analyses. The micro-structure may include the topology of the constituents and their properties as well as the interphase, voids and cracks. However, inclusion of imperfect interphase, voids and cracks pose difficulties because of the presence of material and geometric discontinuities. There exist many homogenization approaches to model the localization processes and capture the effect of micro- and macroscopic material behavior. These techniques estimate both global and local responses accurately using the geometric and material parameters of the individual constituents in the microstructure. These models lead to similar predictions for effective properties and local stress field. However, they do not include the potential micro-cracks in the interphase or voids in the matrix because of the singular nature of crack-tip stress field. Therefore, they are not suitable to capture the effect of damage initiation and evolution on the effective properties, and to construct a damage tensor. Such damage tensor is essential for multi-scale progressive damage prediction analysis.

Because peridynamics is extremely suitable to model material and geometric discontinuities, this study presents a peridynamic approach to predict the effective properties complex heterogeneous structures in the presence of many defects and voids. It permits arbitrary shape and number of reinforcement material, voids and cracks. Along with the effective fully anisotropic material property matrix, it also enables the determination of a damage tensor. The damage tensor enables the transfer of information between micro- and macro-scale analyses; thus, it leads to a viable progressive failure prediction capability. Also, it enables the application of periodic boundary conditions in a natural way without any constraint conditions.

The numerical results concern first the verification of this approach by comparison with those reported in the literature. After verification, effective material property matrix and damage matrix are computed for a heterogeneous micro-structure which includes many matrix cracks and debonds along the fiber-matrix interface.

2 PERIDYNAMICS

As an alternative to the classical continuum mechanics, the bond-based peridynamic (PD) theory introduced by Silling [1] converts the existing governing field equations from their local to nonlocal form by introducing an internal length parameter. Peridynamics (PD) is extremely suitable to model discontinuities such as cracks and interfaces because its governing equation does not include any spatial derivatives; thus remaining valid regardless of discontinuities. In the PD analysis, damage is introduced by removing the interactions between the material points.

In the original bond-based PD, Silling [1] did not distinguish the nature of interactions of material point, with the other points within its family. Therefore, the bond micromodulus was described by only one material constant; this lead to a reduction in independent engineering material constants. This new approach distinguishes interactions through normal and shear bonds as depicted in Fig. 1. These bonds describe either normal or shear deformation. The normal bonds are perpendicular to each other, and aligned with the axes of a Cartesian coordinate system. The shear bonds are off-axes and only lie in the three orthogonal planes of the coordinate system. The family or interaction domain is naturally a cube or a square depending on the dimension of the analysis.

The peridynamic theory concerns the physics of a material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ that interacts with other material points, $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}$ within a certain range, as shown in Fig. 2. The interaction domain of material point $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ is defined by its horizon, δ . Material points $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}$, located within the interaction domain $H_{(i)}$ are called the family members of $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$. As shown in Fig. 2, a pairwise force density vectors, $\mathbf{f}^{(i,j)}$ and $\mathbf{f}^{(j,i)}$ arise from the interaction of material points $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}$ in opposite directions with equal magnitudes.

Figure 1: PD Interactions of material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ with the other points within its family through normal and shear bonds.

Figure 2: Nonlocal interactions between material points $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}$.

The equilibrium of internal force and external force must exist at each material point of a continuum given by

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}} \mathbf{f}^{(i,j)}(\mathbf{u}_{(i)}, \mathbf{u}_{(j)}, \mathbf{u}_{(k)}, \mathbf{u}_{(l)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{(i)}, \mathbf{x}_{(j)}, \mathbf{x}_{(k)}, \mathbf{x}_{(l)}, \dots) V_{(j)} + \mathbf{b}_{(i)} = \rho_{(i)} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_{(i)} \quad i = 1, K. \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{(j)}$ are the displacements of material points $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}$, and $\mathbf{b}_{(i)}$ and $\rho_{(i)}$ are the external force density vector and the density of material at $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$. The range of summation $N_{(i)}$ indicates the number of family members associated with material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$. The total number of material points in the domain is denoted by K . The incremental volume $V_{(j)}$ represents the volume of each material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}$. The PD bond strain vectors, $\mathbf{s}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)}$, bond force density vectors, $\mathbf{f}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)}$ and the micromodulus matrix $\mathbf{c}_{(i)(j)}^{(\alpha)}$ with $(\alpha = 1, \dots, 6)$ for three normal bonds and three shear bonds are explicitly explained by Madenci et al. [2]. The force density vectors, $\mathbf{f}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)}$ for each bond can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{c}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} \mathbf{s}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} \quad \text{with } \alpha = 1, \dots, 6 \quad (2)$$

3 PERIDYNAMIC MODELING OF A UNIT CELL

In the absence of external loads and inertia effects, the equilibrium equation given in Eq. (1) can be rewritten as

$$\sum_{\alpha=1}^6 \sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{f}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)}(\mathbf{u}_{(i)}, \mathbf{u}_{(j)}, \mathbf{u}_{(k)}, \mathbf{u}_{(l)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{(i)}, \mathbf{x}_{(j)}, \mathbf{x}_{(k)}, \mathbf{x}_{(l)}, \dots) V_{(j)} = 0 \quad (3)$$

It is subjected to the periodic boundary conditions specified as

$$\mathbf{u}_{(i)}(\mathbf{x}_{(i)}) = \mathbf{u}_{(i)}(\mathbf{x}_{(i)} + \mathbf{D}) \quad \text{with } \mathbf{D}^T = \{D_1, D_2, D_3\} \quad (4)$$

where D_1, D_2 and D_3 represent the length, width and height of the unit cell, respectively. The parameter $N_{(i)}^{\alpha}$ denotes the number of bond types associated with material point $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$. Another unique feature of the PD UC is the enforcement of periodic boundary conditions. The continuity of both displacement and traction components at the surfaces defining the UC is achieved by completing the family of a material point near the surface or a corner as shown in Fig. 3. The periodic boundary conditions are enforced without any additional constraint conditions. This feature is not present in any other existing methods based on the classical continuum mechanics.

Figure 3: Transfer of information to complete the families of material points near a surface or a corner.

The PD bond strain vectors can be decomposed into its fluctuating and uniform parts as

$$\mathbf{s}_\alpha^{(i,j)} = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} + \bar{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \quad (5)$$

With this decomposition, the bond force vector can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} + \mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \bar{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \quad (6)$$

For a uniform PD strain vector, $\bar{\mathbf{s}}$, it is observed that

$$\mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \bar{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \bar{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the bond force vector can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} + \mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \bar{\mathbf{s}} \quad (8)$$

Thus, the PD equilibrium equation can be recast in the form

$$\sum_{\alpha=1}^6 \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^\alpha} \mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} V_{(j)} \right) = - \sum_{\alpha=1}^6 \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^\alpha} \mathbf{c}_\alpha^{(i,j)} V_{(j)} \right) \bar{\mathbf{s}} \quad i = 1, K \quad (9)$$

This equilibrium equation can be solved for $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_\ell)$ with ($\ell = 1, \dots, 6$) corresponding to each uniform load case, $\bar{\mathbf{s}}_\ell$ specified as

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = \bar{\mathbf{s}}_1 = \{1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0\}^T \quad (10a)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = \bar{\mathbf{s}}_2 = \{0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0\}^T \quad (10b)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = \bar{\mathbf{s}}_3 = \{0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0\}^T \quad (10c)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = \bar{\mathbf{s}}_4 = \{0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0\}^T \quad (10d)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = \bar{\mathbf{s}}_5 = \{0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0\}^T \quad (10e)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = \bar{\mathbf{s}}_6 = \{0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1\}^T \quad (10f)$$

The strain concentration tensor, $\mathbf{H}_\alpha^{(i,j)}$ for each bond type between material points $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}$ is constructed as

$$\mathbf{H}_\alpha^{(i,j)} = \left[\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_1) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_2) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_3) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_4) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_5) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_6) \right] \quad (11)$$

This tensor provides a relation between the applied average strain and the fluctuating PD strain vector for each bond type as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_\alpha^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{H}_\alpha^{(i,j)} \bar{\mathbf{s}} \quad (12)$$

The average PD stress vector in the UC can be achieved by

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^K \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)} V_{(i)} \quad (13)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)}$ representing the PD stress vector at point $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ can be expressed as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^6 \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^{\alpha}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} V_{(j)}}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^{\alpha}} V_{(j)}} \quad (14)$$

in which $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)}$ denotes the stress components associated with normal and shear bonds. They can be obtained from

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \mathbf{s}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \quad (15)$$

with $\mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)}$ representing the material property matrices associated with each bond type. They are explicitly given by Madenci et al. [2]. The stress vector $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)}$ can be decomposed as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} + \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} \quad (16)$$

where

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \quad (17a)$$

and

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \bar{\mathbf{s}}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} = \mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \bar{\mathbf{s}} \quad (17b)$$

Substituting from Eqs. (12) and (17) into Eq. (16) leads to

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} = (\mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} + \mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \mathbf{H}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)}) \bar{\mathbf{s}} \quad (18)$$

The PD stress vector, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)}$ be rewritten as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)} = \bar{\mathbf{s}} \sum_{\alpha=1}^6 (\bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)}) \quad (19)$$

with

$$\bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} V_{(j)}}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^{\alpha}} V_{(j)}} \quad (20a)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{C}_{\alpha}^{(i)(j)} \mathbf{H}_{\alpha}^{(i,j)} V_{(j)}}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{(i)}^{\alpha}} V_{(j)}} \quad (20b)$$

Finally, the PD stress vector at point $\mathbf{x}_{(i)}$ can be

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)} = \mathbf{C}^{(i)} \bar{\mathbf{s}} \quad (21a)$$

where

$$\mathbf{C}^{(i)} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^6 (\bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)}) \quad (21b)$$

This matrix may be non-symmetric due to presence of material discontinuities, voids and cracks. However, it must preserve the symmetry of the stress tensor. Therefore, its anti-symmetric part is disregarded by redefining it in the form

$$\mathbf{C}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^6 (\bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} + \bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)T}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^6 (\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)T}) \quad (22)$$

The averaged stress tensor becomes

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{C}^* \bar{\mathbf{s}} \quad (23)$$

in which \mathbf{C}^* represents the effective property matrix for fully anisotropic material. It is explicitly expressed as

$$\mathbf{C}^* = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{\alpha=1}^6 (\bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} + \bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)T} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\alpha}^{(i)T}) V_{(i)} \quad (24)$$

As discussed by Voyiadjis et al. [3], there exist many different definitions of a damage tensor, \mathbf{D} . A simple and commonly accepted form is defined in terms of the reduction in the stiffness components as

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{C}^{*-1} (\mathbf{C}^* - \mathbf{C}_d) \quad (25)$$

in which \mathbf{C}_d represents the material property matrix in the presence of defects.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS

In order to verify and demonstrate predictions, a UC composed of 53% matrix and 47 % fiber materials is considered as shown in Fig. 4. Its dimensions L , W , and H are equal to unity. Also, the radius of fiber R is calculated as 0.386 mm corresponding to 47% volume fraction of fiber material. The defects can exist in the form of micro-cracks and voids in the matrix, and debonds along the fiber-matrix interface. Though not a limitation, the fiber is placed at the center of the cross-section and cross-sectional geometry does not change through the depth (z -direction) in order to reduce the computational time.

The computational grid of a slice of the UC is shown in Fig. 5. The slice thickness varies depending on the grid spacing on the cross-section on x - y plane. In this model, the length and width of the cell are discretized into 100 by 100 grid, while the depth is represented by 8 layers of grid points. Hence, the grid spacing is specified as $\Delta x = 1/100 = 0.01$ mm, leading to the depth of $H = 8 \times \Delta x = 0.08$ mm.

Figure 4: A UC composed of fiber and matrix with defects.

The periodic boundary conditions are applied as

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= u(x+L, y+W, z+H) \\ v(x, y, z) &= v(x+L, y+W, z+H) \\ w(x, y, z) &= w(x+L, y+W, z+H) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Both constituents are isotropic with Young's modulus $E = 379.3$ GPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.1$ for the fiber, and $E = 68.3$ GPa and $\nu = 0.3$ for the matrix. For verification against the existing methods, the PD UC analysis is first applied to determine its effective material properties.

Figure 5: Computational grid for the UC composed of fiber and matrix constituents without defects.

Employing the PD UC approach, the effective material property matrix for this material is determined as

$$\mathbf{C}^* = \begin{bmatrix} 161.217 & 45.804 & 40.3666 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 45.804 & 161.217 & 40.3666 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 40.3666 & 40.3666 & 230.796 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 54.3382 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 54.3382 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 45.88 \end{bmatrix} \text{ GPa}$$

As expected, the effective material property matrix of the UC without any defects is transversely isotropic. The transversely isotropic engineering material constants are extracted as $E_1 = E_2 = 144.42 \text{ GPa}$, $E_3 = 215.05 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12} = 45.88 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{23} = 54.33 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{13} = 54.33 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.251$, $\nu_{31} = \nu_{32} = 0.195$, and $\nu_{23} = \nu_{13} = 0.131$. Table 1 shows the comparison of the PD UC predictions with those reported in the literature. The comparison shows remarkable agreement between the PD approach and other existing solutions.

	E_3	$E_2 = E_1$	G_{23}	G_{31}	ν_{31}	ν_{12}
PD UC	215.05	144.4	54.3	45.8	0.195	0.251
VAMUCH[4]	215.3	144.1	54.39	45.92	0.195	0.255
FEM [5]	215	144	57.2	45.9	0.19	0.29
HFGMC [6]	215.4	144	54.34	45.83	0.195	0.255
ECM [7]	215.0	143.4	54.3	45.1	0.19	0.26

Table 1: Comparison of the PD UC predictions with other methods.

The PD UC approach is also applied to include cracks and debonds that are arbitrarily inserted at several locations as shown in Fig. 6. The cracks and debonds are created by simply removing the PD bonds. In this figure, the damage representing cracks and debonds is represented by the pink and blue color tones. Note that the points whose horizons intersect with the crack surfaces are also affected as shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 6: PD UC with matrix cracks and fiber-matrix debonds.

This micro-structure involving matrix cracks and debonds along the fiber-matrix interface results in the following effective material property and damage matrices:

$$\mathbf{C}^* = \begin{bmatrix} 145.79 & 38.886 & 36.268 & 0 & 0 & 2.911 \\ 38.886 & 124.975 & 31.987 & 0 & 0 & 1.567 \\ 36.268 & 31.987 & 228.813 & 0 & 0 & 0.491 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 46.117 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 50.738 & 0 \\ 2.911 & 1.567 & 0.491 & 0 & 0 & 39.112 \end{bmatrix} \text{ GPa}$$

and

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.091 & -0.023 & 0.012 & 0 & 0 & -0.016 \\ -0.023 & 0.231 & 0.049 & 0 & 0 & -0.005 \\ 0.012 & 0.049 & -0.00209 & 0 & 0 & 0.002 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.151 & 0.002 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.002 & 0.066 & 0 \\ -0.016 & -0.005 & 0.002 & 0 & 0 & 0.148 \end{bmatrix}$$

where \mathbf{C}^* represents the effective material property matrix with the micro cracks, and \mathbf{D} is the damage tensor reflecting the changes in material properties due to the cracks. The corresponding engineering material constants are calculated as $E_1 = 130.403\text{GPa}$, $E_2 = 112.321\text{GPa}$, $E_3 = 215.44\text{GPa}$, $G_{12} = 39.048\text{GPa}$, $G_{23} = 46.116\text{GPa}$, $G_{31} = 50.738\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.279$, $\nu_{23} = 0.101$, and $\nu_{31} = 0.197$. In comparison to their values prior to cracking, there is a definite reduction and change in material constants as given in Table 2.

	E_1	E_2	E_3	G_{12}	G_{23}	G_{31}	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	ν_{31}
No cracks	144.42	144.42	215.05	45.88	54.33	54.33	0.251	0.131	0.195
With cracks	130.4	112.32	215.44	39.05	46.11	50.74	0.279	0.101	0.197

Table 2: Effect of micro cracks on material constants.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a PD homogenization approach to predict effective material property matrix of heterogeneous materials. It provides the ability to determine a damage matrix emerging from the presence of micro cracks, debonds in the interphase and voids. They are modeled by simply breaking the peridynamic bonds. The periodic boundary conditions are imposed without any constraint conditions. Furthermore, it provides the ability to determine the local stress and strain fields within the unit cell. This capability can serve as a bridge between macro-, meso- and micro-scale analyses for progressive failure of composites.

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